

ANALYTICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON HIGH-TEMPERATURE HIGH-VELOCITY IMPACT LIMIT FOR C/C COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Explosively formed debris at low earth orbit is one of the most severe hypervelocity impact loading threats to space shuttle. The collision induced crack or perforation would lead to an unzipping of the thermal protection system (TPS) of the impacted shuttle when the impact occurs in their re-entry stage. So far, SiC coated C/C composite (RCC as abbreviated) as a candidate material for TPS have not been studied sufficiently on their mechanical protection performance. The hypervelocity impact characteristics of RCC at temperatures of 25°C to 1400°C were analysed and discussed in this paper. The experimental test programs were implemented with a converted light gas gun system and results were presented with various impact factors being considered. Furthermore, corresponding simulations were carried out and the morphologies of perforated holes from numerical results were consistent with those observed from tests results. Additionally, a semi-empirical and semi-analytical model was developed and successfully used for predicting the residual velocity and trajectory of the projectiles during the impact. Eventually, comparisons of the ballistic impact response predictions with the experimental results were presented and discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Explosively formed debris at low earth orbit is one of the most severe hypervelocity impact loading threats to space shuttle. The collision induced crack or perforation would lead to an unzipping of the thermal protection system (TPS) of the impacted shuttle when the impact occurs in its re-entry stage.

Since dual metallic protective structure for spacecraft was initially suggested by Whipple [1] in 1947, many analytical models have been proposed and developed to investigate the response during the hypervelocity impact [2]. However, little works have been done on the protection performance of TPS under ultra-high temperature by far [3], and little meaningful high-temperature high-velocity test data were available for the general case of obliquely incident projectile.

Reinforced carbon-carbon composite (RCC as abbreviated), as a promising material for TPS, were used as the impact target in this study. In this paper, a semi-empirical analytical model was developed and successfully used for predicting the impact response of RCC. The objective of this paper is to provide general design guidelines for thermal protection shields with the proposed model and experimental data.

2 ANALYTICAL MODEL DESCRIPTION

The protective capacity of the carbon matrix composites should be predicted at the design phase. Protective system design for spacecraft was initially suggested by Whipple [1]. In this part, a phenomenological based analytical model, which referred to the distribution pattern of the splashed fragments during the hypervelocity impact test, was established base on some reasonable assumptions.

Fig. 1 Schematic of oblique hypervelocity impact of a panel

Spherical projectile hit the panel at an impact angle, carrying enormous kinetic energy. Panel was crashed into pieces by shockwave and the fragments mainly consisted two typical debris clouds (see Fig. 1), “normal” debris cloud penetrated inward to the witness plate, while “ricochet” one travelled backwards, away from the target. Based on our previous discovery, the trajectory of projectile shifted slightly but no in-line debris cloud was observed, so it might be assumed rigid during the test.

The penetration process was governed by the conservation law of energy, and it can be formulated as Eq.(1):

$$m_p V_p^2 / 2 = m_p V_f^2 / 2 + m_r V_r^2 / 2 + m_t V_t^2 / 2 + W_i + W_f \quad (1)$$

The overall process was assumed that the energy associated with light flash could be neglected. Since local shearing could be ignored [4], the loss of energy was merely caused by dynamic resistive force, Thus W_i could be written by the following expression, i.e.:

$$W_i = \int_0^{\frac{t_w}{\cos \theta_p}} A_h \sigma \left(\frac{t_w}{\cos \theta_p} - x \right) dx = \frac{\pi d_h t_w^2 \sigma}{2 \cos^2 \theta_p} \quad (2)$$

In this paper, the impact of projectile and the cylindrical plug were assumed inelastic, which would lead to maximum kinetic energy loss. Therefore W_f was estimated by momentum and energy considerations [5], i.e.

$$W_f = m_p m_w V_p^2 / 2 (m_p + m_w) \quad (3)$$

Here m_w is the total mass of fragments, thus $m_w = m_r + m_t$.

The conservation law of momentum in normal and tangential directions yields the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} m_p V_p \cos \theta_p &= m_p V_f \cos \theta_f + m_t V_t \cos \theta_t - m_r V_r \sin \theta_r \\ m_p V_p \sin \theta_p &= m_p V_f \sin \theta_f + m_t V_t \sin \theta_t + m_r V_r \cos \theta_r \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The mass of normal debris cloud and normal debris trajectory angle could be estimated with the following relationship [6, 7]:

$$\frac{m_t}{m_p} = -0.433 \left(\frac{t_w}{d_p} \right)^{0.605} \left(\frac{V_p}{C_w} \right)^{0.112} \cos^{-1.693} \theta_p + 1.065 \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\theta_t}{\theta_p} = 0.471 \left(\frac{t_w}{d_p} \right)^{-0.054} \left(\frac{V_p}{C_w} \right)^{-0.049} \cos^{1.134} \theta_p \quad (6)$$

The sound velocity of $C_w = 1.91 \text{ km/s}$ [8] is assigned for carbon/carbon composite.

The normal component of the projectile residual velocity was assumed as high as that of the normal debris transmitted velocity, and then the expression can be written as follows:

$$V_t \cos \theta_t = V_f \cos \theta_f \quad (7)$$

$m_p = \pi d_p^3 \rho_p / 6$ and $m_w = \pi d_h^2 t_w \rho_w / 4$ can be obtained for the spherical projectiles used in this paper, and the trajectory angle of the ricochet debris could be recorded by experimental method. Thus the residual unknowns (V_f V_r V_t θ_r) could be solved by the empirical equations as well as simplifying assumptions above.

For the normal impact cases ($\theta_p = \theta_r = \theta_t = \theta_f = 0$), the residual velocity V_f could be simplified with the following equation:

$$V_f = \left(m_p V_p - m_t V_t + \sqrt{m_r^2 V_r^2 - 2m_r \cdot W_s} \right) / m_p \quad (8)$$

A zero-residual velocity ($V_f = 0$) of projectile can be defined as the critical state during the normal impact. The mass of the debris cloud and velocity of the ricochet debris cloud can be estimated by the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} m_t &= 0 \\ m_r &= m_w = \pi d_{hc}^2 t_w \rho_w / 4 \\ m_p &= \pi d_{pc}^3 \rho_p / 6 \\ V_r &= V_p \times \left[-0.514 \times (t_w / d_{pc})^{0.679} \times (V_p / c_w)^{-0.064} \times \cos^{-0.936} \theta_p + 1.046 \right] \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Where $d_{hm} = 2.20 d_p \rho_p^{1/3} V_p^{1/3} - 0.36$, $d_{hc} = 2.20 d_p \rho_p^{1/3} V_p^{1/3} - 0.36$ [9]. Backwash velocity V_r in Eq. (8) was replaced with a simplified empirical equation [10, 11].

Thus, critical projectile diameters d_{pc} can be obtained as function of the impact velocity V_p with Eq. (8). This characteristic curve of ballistic limit was used to predict the penetration performance of structures. The analytical model was valid for thin target panels and the cases where the ricochet debris cloud caused by the projectile couldn't be ignored.

3 EXPERIMENTS

3.1 SPECIMENS

The structure of SiC-C/C composites was presented in Fig. 2, and the thickness of oxidation coating on C/C composite was about 100 μm .

Fig. 2 Architecture of the SiC-C/C composites

Fig. 3 showed the impact targets used in this paper.

Fig. 3 Impact targets (a) Dimensions (unit: mm) (b) Picture of SiC-C/C

In the experimental test program, spherical projectiles with different diameters and velocities hit the specimens at various incident angles, and Si_3N_4 and stainless steel were selected respectively as the materials of projectiles. More detailed parameters were recorded in Table 1.

3.2 Impact tests

A two-stage light gas gun (LGG) equipped with fast electric heating system were custom-made and employed during the experimental tests. Projectile was accelerated at a specified velocity and hit the target which was subjected to high temperatures. The ballistic behavior of the specimens was investigated by oblique impact. Three specified incident angles, i.e. 15° , 30° and 45° , were set during tests.

Fig. 4 showed a general sketch of the oblique impact test. The incident angle was adjusted by rotating the specimen in a certain angle around the impact center point, thus the distance between witness plate and center point were kept constantly throughout the experiments. A6061-T6 aluminium alloy witness plate was set to observe and measure the debris cloud distribution and crater location after the test, as demonstrated in Fig. 5. The post-impact trajectory of the projectile θ_f could be calculated by the equation below:

$$\theta_f = \theta_p - \arctan(d/t) \quad (10)$$

The testing and measuring apparatus along with experimental procedure stayed the same with our previous work, and more details could be found in ref.[3].

Fig. 4 Schematic of the impact test

Fig. 5 Witness plate (RCC8)

3.3 SHEAR STRENGTH

Split Hopkinson pressure bar (SHPB) system was employed to measure the dynamic shear resistance of the carbon-carbon composites subjected to high temperature. Li et al. [12] did numerous

studies on the dynamic mechanical properties and constitutive model of C/C composites. As low oxidation resistance of carbon matrix, an improved SHPB facility were used to obtained the dynamic mechanical properties of the specimen at a high temperature. So far, there were quite few literatures investigating the dynamic strength of the needle punched C/C at the high temperature up to 1500°C. Therefore, an engineering model was proposed by Wen [14]: the dynamic resistive pressure could be expressed as a function of that in quasi-static, i.e. $\sigma_d = \beta \sqrt{\rho_w / \sigma_s} V_p \sigma_s$, so the equivalent resistive pressure formula was written as:

$$\sigma = \left(1 + \beta \sqrt{\rho_w / \sigma_s} V_p\right) \sigma_s \quad (11)$$

Where the empirical constant β was set to 1.5 [13].

The quasi-static shear strength σ_s of C/C composite could be obtained by experimental method, and the shear strength tests were all carried out along with the thickness direction of specimen. Impact tests were performed separately according to the incident angles.

3.4 TEST RESULTS

The RCC panels were took as targets, and the size and distance of perforated elliptical hole and crater were measured manually after the test campaign, as listed in Table 1. No geometric deformations of projectiles were observed during the penetration process. Average size of holes on the front and back surfaces was calculated and recorded in Table 1 for each case.

NO.	Projectile diameter (mm)	Projectile material	Impact angel (degree)	Panel material	Panel thickness (mm)	V_p (m/s)	T (°C)	Test result*	d (mm)	Elliptical hole size # (mm)	
										a	b
RCC1	2	Si ₃ N ₄	45	SiC-C/C	5	1340	815	Perf	--	8.55	6.22
RCC2	3	Si ₃ N ₄	45	SiC-C/C	5	2230	1420	Perf	--	15.16	12.60
RCC3	2	Si ₃ N ₄	15	SiC -C/C	5	2740	1430	Perf	28	10.45	9.85
RCC4	2	Si ₃ N ₄	30	SiC -C/C	5	2390	1206	Perf	--	10.70	9.15
RCC5	3	Si ₃ N ₄	30	SiC -C/C	5	2970	830	Perf	30	14.05	14.90
RCC6	3	Si ₃ N ₄	15	SiC -C/C	5	1490	1232	Perf	--	9.25	10.90
RCC7	5	Si ₃ N ₄	45	SiC -C/C	5	2820	1205	Perf	20	23.43	19.93
RCC8	5	Si ₃ N ₄	30	SiC -C/C	5	1760	1401	Perf	44	17.30	15.15
RCC9	5	Si ₃ N ₄	15	SiC -C/C	5	2570	822	Perf	15	18.96	18.30
RCC10	3	steel	15	SiC -C/C	5	2990	1229	Perf	23	13.92	13.83
RCC11	3	steel	15	SiC -C/C	5	3130	1267	Perf	27	14.76	14.68
RCC12	3	steel	15	SiC -C/C	5	2720	18	Perf	25	16.28	15.62

*Perf: the specimen was perforated; No Perf: the specimen was not perforated.

#a: ellipse length, b: elliptical short diameter.

Table 1 Oblique impact test results

In the first nine oblique tests, the effects of projectile diameter and impact angle were investigated by using orthogonal test method, while the panel thickness and material of both projectile and target remained uniformly. Crater distance d in RCC1, RCC2, RCC4 and RCC6 was lost because of human carelessness. Another three experiments were performed with steel projectile in contrast with that made up of Si₃N₄. RCC12 was carried out at the room temperature, meanwhile the other two specimens were heated to above 1200°C. Fig. 6 shows general morphology of plug shaped hole in RCC8 test and rough edges were observed. The hypervelocity impact induced ultra-high temperature gasified the matrix then carbon fibers were shattered by the penetrating projectile. Eventually broken fibers distributed intricately around the hole.

Fig. 6 Damaged hole after test (#RCC8)

There were no obvious wrinkles and deflections around the perforated hole, as shown in Fig. 6. The perforation mechanism of composite subjected to hypervelocity impact was dominated by shaped plug formation, causing shear failure in the target. For all cases, the trajectories of the ricochet debris were also evaluated by images taken with high speed camera.

The quasi-static compressive mechanical properties of the specimens at various testing temperatures were obtained experimentally, as depicted in Fig. 7. These plots within 1600°C centigrade were used to evaluate the σ_s of the two typical C/C composite specimens ignoring the effect of thin anti-oxidative coating. When the testing temperature exceeded 1800°C, the compressive strength of the specimen decreased due to the effect of thermal softening.

Fig. 7 Out-of-plane compressive properties of C/C composite

4 DISCUSSION

Due to the strong impact flash excited after the panels were perforated, the residual velocities of projectiles and the distributions of normal fragments were not obtained by this work. Deflection angles of projectile θ_f calculated through experimental results were used to validate those derived by the analytical model. The experimental results were compared against the analytical solutions, as presented in Table 2.

NO.	Impact angle (rad)	Deflection angle from experiments (rad)	Deflection angle from predictions (rad)	Err%
RCC3	0.262	0.105	0.080	24.0
RCC7	0.785	0.488	0.355	27.3
RCC8	0.524	0.308	0.304	1.3
RCC9	0.262	0.168	0.141	16.0
RCC10	0.262	0.132	0.119	9.8
RCC11	0.262	0.129	0.115	11.1
RCC12	0.262	0.134	0.111	17.1

Table 2 Comparisons of damage area

The maximum relative error of the analytical solutions was 27.3% in test RCC7 and the predictions were slightly lower than the experimental data. Schonberg et al. [14] had conducted the hypervelocity tests and established the empirical equation of deflection angle by fitting the experimental data. The relationship takes the form of Eq. (12).

$$\theta_f/\theta_p = 0.427(V_p/C_w)^{-0.318} (\sin\theta_p)^{-0.255} (t_w/d_p)^{-0.436} \quad (12)$$

Fig. 8 presented the comparison between analytical calculations and empirical results of the deflection angle. All the analytical results corresponding to the oblique impact test conditions were performed and compared respectively by projectile material.

Fig. 8 Comparisons of analytical and experimental results of projectile deflection angle

It indicated that the analytical predictions derived in section 2 matched well with curves obtained from the reference. θ_f provided by Eq.(12) showed a downward trend with the increase of impact velocity when the projectile diameter was fixed. Analytical model described in this paper were established without every term of energy loss being considered, as well as built based on empirical relationships, as a result, small gaps of θ_f were observed between theoretical and experimental results. In summary, the analytical model could be applied to make predictions about the hypervelocity impact.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper has presented a novel semi-theoretical semi-phenomenological model for advanced C/C composite specimens subjected to hypervelocity impact at temperatures of 25 to 1430 °C. The experimental results relating to a wide range of impact conditions have been successfully obtained by using customized two-stage light-gas gun system. The response of ballistic impact under various conditions have been investigated with the validated model. By comparing the predictions and experimental results, conclusions can be obtained as follows:

(1) The distribution of post-impact fragments and trajectory of unbroken projectiles through the hypervelocity impact process are considered phenomenologically when establishing the analytical model, and the new model could provide a more accurate prediction than the tradition one available in open literature.

(2) Comparison of the trajectory of projectile predictions and data from experimental test program in this paper shows a good agreement in both tendency and magnitude.

A general guideline is provided with the proposed analytical model and the experimental data on designing the TPS of the spacecraft structures, considering the effects of the impact pairs, impact velocity, impact angle, working temperature and projectile diameter.

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